

42 **INTRODUCTION**

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Cardiovascular disease is the leading mortality cause worldwide (WHO, 2021). With the current rising demographic trend of population ageing, this burden is expected to increase further (Joseph et al., 2017). Ongoing urbanization is another crucial demographic shift, with estimates predicting that by 2050 around 70% of the world's population will live in urban areas (Baeumler et al., 2021). Urban areas often lack available greenspace and, simultaneously, have high concentrations of ambient air pollution, noise, and heat, all of which have been associated with a higher risk of cardiovascular problems.

Several studies have described the association between greenspace exposure and reduced cardiovascular morbidity and mortality risk (Fong et al., 2018; Twohig-Bennett and Jones, 2018; Yang et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2022). Various mechanisms have been proposed to explain how greenspaces may reduce risk of cardiovascular disease. These include mitigating air pollution, reducing noise and excess heat, lowering stress levels, stimulating physical activity, and enhancing social contacts and cohesion (Hartig et al., 2014; James et al., 2015; Markevych et al., 2017; Nieuwenhuijsen et al., 2017; Marselle et al., 2021).

So far, the investigations on greenspace and cardiovascular health have focused on macrovascular health (i.e. the condition of the large blood vessels in the body). The microvasculature—the intricate network of tiny blood vessels within our body—is an essential compartment to be monitored as early markers of cardiovascular conditions, given their involvement in the pathogenesis of these conditions (Streese et al., 2021). Its primary role is to ensure efficient perfusion, delivering nutrients and oxygen to tissues. While the micro- and macrovasculature are interconnected phenotypes within the circulatory system, they also function as distinct and independent predictors (Streese et al., 2022; Hanssen et al., 2022). Nevertheless, studies investigating the association between greenspace and microvascular status are still lacking.

Fundus photography has emerged as a promising non-invasive, cost-effective method to assess subclinical changes in the microvascular system (Louwies et al., 2013; Provost et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2019; Guo et al., 2020; Streese et al., 2021; Hanssen et al., 2022). Fundus images enable the quantification and characterization of the vessel diameters of retinal arterioles and venules. A recent review presented conclusive evidence on the association between retinal microvascular blood vessel diameter changes and higher cardiovascular risk, disease, and mortality (Mutlu et al., 2015; Seidelmann et al., 2016; Rijks et al., 2018; Hanssen et al., 2022). Evaluating the retinal microvasculature could help better understand cardiovascular disease aetiology and early disease detection.

The current study assessed the relationship between exposure to greenspace and retinal microvascular status in healthy adults by applying a repeated-measurement design. We hypothesized that higher exposure to greenspace could be associated with better retinal microvasculature health (i.e., wider arterioles and narrower venules).

90 **METHODS**

91

92 **Study design and population**

93

94 This study was conducted in the context of the health substudy of the multicenter Physical
95 Activity through Sustainable Transport Approaches (PASTA) project (Dons et al., 2015;
96 Gerike et al., 2016). Data on subclinical cardiovascular biomarkers were collected in a real-
97 world monitoring substudy in three European cities in the south, center, and north of Europe,
98 namely Barcelona (Spain), Antwerp (Belgium), and London (UK). By completing the online
99 PASTA survey, participants provided baseline information on sociodemographic variables,
100 including age, sex, self-reported height and weight, nationality, education level, and
101 employment status. Eligibility criteria for substudy participation were: adults aged 18-65 years
102 old, self-reported body mass index (BMI) <30, current non-smokers (i.e., have quit more than
103 24 months before the start of the study), healthy medical history (i.e., no self-reported
104 cardiorespiratory or neurological condition), and non-pregnant women.

105 Substudy data collection occurred at three time points during different seasons between
106 February 2015 and March 2016 (Avila-Palencia et al., 2019). Collected repeated health
107 measurements relevant to our study were: retina images, body weight, and blood pressure (BP;
108 systolic [SBP] and diastolic [DBP]). All three involved centers followed a standardized
109 procedure to collect these health measurements (i.e., applying the same steps following the
110 same order in a controlled setting). Before initiating data collection, research staff from each
111 participating center underwent joint training at the research center in Antwerp. To minimize
112 the potential influence of circadian biological rhythms, all health measurements were
113 assembled on weekdays during the late afternoon (15-20h). Additionally, in the hours before
114 the health assessment, participants were requested to follow specific guidelines regarding
115 dietary intake, physical activity, and environmental tobacco smoke (detailed guidelines
116 available elsewhere (Avila-Palencia et al., 2019)).

117

118 All participants signed written informed consent. The study protocol (Dons et al., 2015) was
119 approved by each participating center's ethical committee [Ethics board of University Hospital
120 of Antwerp (Belgium), Clinical Research Ethics Committee of the Municipal Health Care
121 Barcelona (Spain), Imperial College Research Ethics Committee London (UK)].

122

123 **Surrounding greenness**

124

125 Greenness surrounding each participant's home and work/school location was characterized
126 using two vegetation indices (VI): the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)
127 (Tucker, 1979) and the Modified Soil-adjusted Vegetation Index 2 (MSAVI2) (Qi et al.,
128 1994a). Atmospherically corrected cloud-free satellite images were retrieved from Landsat 8,
129 available at the spatial resolution of 30 m x 30 m (Gorelick et al., 2017). Detailed information
130 on retrieving the satellite imagery is available in the supplementary material (S1.1).

131

132 Surrounding greenness was assigned as both seasonal and annual exposure. Time-varying
133 seasonal greenness included matching the different data collection time points to its
134 corresponding meteorological season, whereas annual greenness represented the highest
135 vegetation levels during the entire study period.

136

137 We calculated the average index value around the geocoded address at each location and for
138 each time point across circular Euclidean buffers of 100 m, 300 m, and 500 m, resulting for
139 each participant in 36 seasonal greenness measures [i.e. 3 (seasons) * 2 (vegetation indices) *
140 2 (locations) * 3 (buffers)] and 6 annual measures [i.e. 1 (vegetation index) * 2 (locations) * 3
141 (buffers)].

142

143 **Retinal vessel metrics**

144

145 The retinal microvascular status was evaluated using fundus photography. At each of the three
146 data collection visits, the fundus of the participant's right eye was meticulously captured as
147 part of the study protocol (Dons et al., 2015; Gerike et al., 2016). Prior large-scale studies
148 (Leung et al., 2003; Wong et al., 2004), have demonstrated a strong correlation in retinal vessel
149 diameters between eyes. Consequently, measuring retinal vessel diameters from one eye could
150 provide adequate information indicative of a person's retinal vessel caliber. At least two good
151 quality, high-resolution fundus images per participant were obtained by a Canon CR-2 plus 45°
152 6.3-megapixel digital nonmydriatic retinal camera (Hospithera, Brussels, Belgium). Image
153 processing was done using MONA REVA software (VITO, Mol, Belgium; Khan et al., 2022).
154 Selection of consistent and similar retinal regions across all fundus images was obtained in
155 MONA REVA by defining an annular region centered on the optic disc, with the inner and
156 outer radii of the annulus set at 1.5 and 3.0 times the radius of the optic disc, respectively. Next,
157 the MONA REVA algorithm automatically segmented the retinal vessels. The segmentation
158 algorithm is based on a multiscale line filtering algorithm inspired by Nguyen and coworkers
159 (2013). Post-processing steps included double thresholding, blob extraction, removal of small
160 connected regions, and filling holes. The diameters of the retinal arterioles and venules that
161 passed entirely through the circumferential zone 0.5 to 1 disc diameter from the optic disc
162 margin were calculated automatically. The trained grader, masked to participant characteristics,
163 verified and corrected vessel diameters and vessel labels (arteriole or venule) with the semi-
164 automated MONA REVA vessel editing toolbox. All paired fundus images of the same
165 participant were presented in batch to facilitate the selection of the same individual retinal
166 vessel segments. The diameters of the 6 largest arterioles and 6 largest venules were used in
167 the revised Parr-Hubbard-Knudtson formula (Knudtson et al., 2003) for calculating the Central
168 Retinal Arteriolar Equivalent (CRAE) and Central Retinal Venular Equivalent (CRVE). The
169 CRAE and CRVE were averaged out for each participant at each time point to minimize
170 random variation in retinal vessel diameter due to different stages of the cardiac cycle
171 (Knudtson et al., 2004) and were expressed in micrometers (μm).

172

173 **Statistical analysis**

174

175 *Main analyses*

176 We developed linear mixed-effects models with the participants as the random effect to
177 evaluate the association between predictors of greenspace (seasonal NDVI) and retinal
178 microvascular metrics (CRAE or CRVE) as outcomes. We defined two models similar to prior
179 research (Adar et al., 2010; Louwies et al., 2013; Provost et al., 2017). Model 1 (M1) included
180 age, sex, BMI (kg/m^2), nationality (*country of study vs. foreign*), education level (*secondary vs.*
181 *higher education*), employment status (*full-time vs. part-time, student or other*), area-level
182 percentage of low-educated and foreign origin as census-derived indicators of neighborhood
183 socioeconomic position, temperature, relative humidity, and city (*Antwerp, Barcelona or*
184 *London*) as fixed effect predictors. Model 2 (M2) was further adjusted for fellow vessel

185 diameter (i.e., for CRVE in CRAE outcome models and vice versa), correcting for the shared
186 microvascular physiological status between CRAE and CRVE and potential confounding
187 thereof (Adar et al., 2010; Louwies et al., 2013; Provost et al., 2017).

188

189 *Further analyses*

190 We repeated the main models in additional analyses using seasonal MSAVI2 and annual NDVI
191 as alternative greenspace metrics. We furthermore developed a combined exposure index by
192 averaging home and work/school greenness by weighing the daytime (12 hours per day) that
193 participants spent at work (i.e., self-reported average weekly working hours for each participant
194 as obtained in the baseline survey) or at school (i.e., 8 h; (Dadvand et al., 2015)), and at home
195 (home = daytime - work/school).

196

197 *Sensitivity analyses*

198 We assessed the robustness of our findings in sensitivity analyses. First, we further adjusted
199 the main models for personal time-varying exposure to black carbon (BC; more details on air
200 pollution exposure assessment can be found in supplementary material (S1.2)). Second, we
201 additionally adjusted our models for the mean arterial blood pressure (MAP; [$MAP = (2/3 * DBP) + (1/3 * SBP)$]). Blood pressure is associated with retinal vessel diameter dimensions
203 (Streese et al., 2021). We correct the models for this effect by taking into account MAP, which
204 is a central driver to ensure that a sufficient level of perfusion is maintained for the function of
205 all organs. Further information on the assessment of blood pressure in our study can be found
206 in the supplement (S2). Last, we alternatively fitted our models with the participant and city as
207 random effects, nesting participants within their respective cities.

208

209 We explored the potential modification of the association between each greenspace measure
210 and retinal microvasculature by sex through evaluating the goodness of fit of models,
211 comparing models with and without additive interaction terms using the likelihood-ratio test
212 (LRT), and fitting sex-stratified models.

213

214 Regression results are presented as beta coefficients (β) and 95% confidence intervals (95%
215 CI) for each interquartile range (IQR) increase in each greenspace indicator and each buffer
216 size. All analyses were performed in R version 3.6.2 (R Core Team, 2019) with lme4 (V.1.1-
217 26; Bates et al., 2015), lmerTest (V.0.9-37; Zeileis and Hothorn, 2002) and base and dependency
218 packages.

219

220 **RESULTS**

221

222 **Study population and greenspace exposure**

223

224 A total of 114 out of 122 individuals participating in the PASTA health substudy were eligible
225 for the current analysis. Participants with missing geographic coordinates (n=7; 5.7%) or
226 missing covariate information (n=1; 0.8%) were excluded. Observations at three different time
227 points were completed for most participants (69.3%). For the remaining participants, one or
228 two time point(s) were available (i.e., 3.5% and 27.2%, respectively), resulting in a total
229 number of 303 repeated observations (Table S1).

230

231 The baseline characteristics of the study population are presented in Table 1. Women
232 represented 53.5% of the total study population. Participants had a median (IQR) age of 33

233 (12.8) years and a BMI of 22.7 (4.5). The majority of individuals had the nationality of the
234 country of study (86%), obtained a higher education level (89.5%), and were mainly full-time
235 employees (74.6%). Individual baseline characteristics did not differ significantly between
236 cities (Table S1), whereas outcomes and greenspace measures did (Table 2).

237
238 The median (IQR) overall CRAE and CRVE values were 160.8 (19.3) and 235.6 (25.8),
239 respectively (Table 2). Levels of surrounding greenness were lower (p-value: 0.01) in
240 Barcelona compared to Antwerp and London at both locations (i.e., home and work/school).
241 Additionally, in Antwerp and London, observed levels of surrounding greenness were higher
242 (p-value: 0.01) around the home compared to the work/school location, while greenness levels
243 at both locations were similar in Barcelona. We observed strong positive correlations between
244 the greenspace across different buffer sizes at each location (0.75-0.98) (Table S2) and between
245 vegetation indices seasonal NDVI and MSAVI2, and annual NDVI (0.88-0.99) (Table S3).

246

247 **Association between greenspace and retinal microvasculature**

248

249 *Main analyses*

250 In the first model (M1), regression coefficients for the association between surrounding
251 greenness and CRAE or CRVE were predominantly negative for all locations (Table 3). After
252 adjustment for fellow vessel diameter (M2), effect estimates attenuated, especially for CRAE,
253 where associations became weaker and were no longer statistically significant. Attenuation was
254 stronger for larger buffers compared to smaller buffers. There were no associations between
255 home surrounding greenness and CRAE or CRVE. In contrast, for surrounding greenness at
256 work/school we observed a smaller retinal venular diameter (CRVE) with higher greenness
257 levels in both models [M2 (NDVI) 300m: -3.043, 95%CI -5.460,-0.627; 500m: -3.886, 95%CI
258 -6.404,-1.369].

259

260 *Further analyses*

261 Participants spent on average 46.3 hours a week at home and 37.7 hours at work/school during
262 the daytime. Findings for the daytime index (i.e., combined home and work/school greenspace
263 exposure) were in line with those for the work/school location (Table S4-S5). Results with
264 seasonal MSAVI2 as an alternative exposure measure were nearly identical to those with
265 seasonal NDVI (Table S4). Effect estimates with annual NDVI were similar, though slightly
266 stronger than seasonal NDVI, especially for CRVE (Table S5). Following an analysis where
267 we corrected for population density, the observed patterns an interpretation remained
268 unchanged (Table S6). In the end, we investigated whether a non-movers only analysis would
269 change our conclusions, but it did not. Table S7 contains the findings of this investigation.

270

271 *Sensitivity analyses*

272 Sensitivity analyses did not alter our main findings (Table S8). The main results remained
273 robust for further adjustment for BC. Regression models additionally accounting for blood
274 pressure (MAP) were consistent with the results of the primary analyses, except for the inverse
275 association between CRAE and work/school greenness that lost its statistical significance in
276 M1. MAP correction was applied because it is known that blood pressure is associated with
277 retinal vessel dimensions. When city as a random effect was included in alternative linear
278 mixed regression models, associations between CRVE and home greenness became more
279 robust in both main models (NDVI 300m *M1*: -4.893, 95%CI -8.798,-0.989; *M2*: -3.336,
280 95%CI -6.670,-0.001).

281 **Effect modification by sex**

282

283 In our study sample, women were on average younger (p-value: 0.04), had a lower BMI (p-
284 value: 0.01), and had wider retinal vessel diameters (p-values for CRAE: 0.04 and CRVE: 0.05)
285 than men (Table S9). Overall, the goodness of fit of models did not improve significantly after
286 including an interaction term between surrounding greenness and sex (LRT p-value between
287 0.10-0.90), except for the associations with CRVE in M1 at the home location for the 300m
288 and 500m (LRT p-values: 0.05 and 0.04, respectively) (Table S10). Sex-stratified analyses
289 suggested stronger associations in women than in men with CRAE and CRVE (Figure 1). The
290 strongest relations were observed in women between home surrounding greenness and CRVE
291 [M1 (NDVI) 300m: -11.399, 95%CI -18.355,-4.443, LRT p-value 0.04; 500m: -10.691, 95%CI
292 -17.558,-3.823, LRT p-value 0.05] (Table S10). However, associations attenuated after
293 adjustment for fellow vessel diameter (M2) (Figure 1 and Table S10).

294

295 **DISCUSSION**

296

297 To our knowledge, this study is the first to assess the relationship between greenspace and
298 retinal microvasculature. This study benefitted from data on greenspace exposure at home and
299 workplace/school combined with three repeated measures of retinal microvasculature among
300 participants from three cities in the south, center, and north of Europe with different climates
301 and contexts. We observed consistent associations between higher levels of surrounding
302 greenness and smaller retinal venular diameters, as measured by CRVE, with potentially
303 stronger associations for women. Our findings for CRAE were not conclusive. These
304 observations remained robust in different sensitivity analyses.

305

306 **Interpretation of results in light of prior research**

307

308 No prior studies are available on the relation between greenspace and retinal microvasculature.
309 Therefore, a direct comparison of our findings with other studies is impossible. Our findings,
310 however, are consistent with the growing body of evidence linking greenspace exposure to
311 better cardiovascular health (Fong et al., 2018; Twohig-Bennett and Jones, 2018; Yang et al.,
312 2021; Liu et al., 2022). Our studied outcome has been identified as a reliable, independent and
313 promising biomarker to improve cardiovascular risk prediction and risk stratification,
314 complementing traditional risk factors (Liu et al., 2019; Guo et al., 2020; Streese et al., 2021;
315 Hanssen et al., 2022). Retinal microvascular alterations (i.e., narrower arterioles [CRAE] and
316 wider venules [CRVE]) signal an increased risk for cardiovascular outcomes, including
317 hypertension, coronary artery disease, heart failure, stroke, and cardiovascular mortality (Mutlu
318 et al., 2015; Seidelmann et al., 2016; Rijks et al., 2018; Hanssen et al., 2022). More specifically,
319 Deng et al. (2014) reported that wider venules were associated with an increased risk of
320 hypertension with an odd's ratio of 1.14 per 20- μ m difference. Even though the venular caliber
321 changes we have seen are smaller, they could nevertheless have a significant impact on public
322 health if they cause an odd's ratio to rise. Even small changes in population risk can have a big
323 impact on the overall burden of disease. If the population is broadly exposed to less green, this
324 light increase in the risk of hypertension could result in considerable rise in the number of
325 people who get hypertension. Thus, understanding the relationship between green space and
326 microcirculation emphasizes the need of environmental interventions as a public health
327 strategy, such as increasing access to green spaces, in the framework of preventative medicine.

328

329 In our study, we observed inverse associations for both CRAE and CRVE with nearly all
330 greenspace measures (i.e., narrower retinal vessel diameters with higher levels of green), with
331 associations being more robust for CRVE. In mutually adjusted models (M2) with CRAE as
332 the outcome, estimates weakened and lost their statistical significance after including CRVE
333 as a predictor in the models. With CRVE as the outcome, associations with surrounding
334 greenness remained when mutually adjusting. Both retinal vessel types are part of the same
335 complex microvascular network (Hester and Hammer, 2002). Further adjusting for fellow
336 vessel diameter enabled us to isolate better the independent association with greenspace on
337 both vessel types (CRAE and CRVE). However, a potential over-adjustment could not be ruled
338 out, given their high correlation.

339
340 Associations in both main models (M1 and M2) were stronger at work/school and for the
341 daytime index than at home. These findings agree with another study assessing greenness levels
342 at multiple locations (Dadvand et al., 2015). However, a note of caution is due to comparability
343 between the different studies. Yet, greenspace exposure at locations other than the residence
344 has been rarely assessed despite its relevance in representing actual exposure (Nieuwenhuijsen
345 et al., 2017). Consistent with findings of our previous studies (Dadvand et al., 2015), we found
346 more indications for potentially more robust associations for greenspace exposure at
347 work/school, which might be due the more active daily time that participants spent in these
348 microenvironments, while engaging in their main activities.

349 We assessed greenness by maximizing both seasonal and annual exposure levels. Observed
350 patterns were similar with both indicators. Such finding may suggest the potential independent
351 relation between retinal microvascular health and nature (i.e. captured by greenness),
352 regardless of its current greenness levels (i.e. seasonal variation).

353
354 Greenspace distribution differed across the three participating cities. Sensitivity analyses,
355 including a random effect for between-city variability, strengthened associations between home
356 greenness and retinal venules (CRVE). These minor association differences may be driven by
357 contextual sources of heterogeneity independent of data collection. As for the latter,
358 standardized protocols were used in all participating centers minimizing potential
359 methodological inconsistencies to the greatest extent possible.

360
361 The main results did not change notably after adjustment for ambient air pollution, an
362 environmental risk factor previously associated with retinal microvasculature health (Adar et
363 al., 2010; Louwies et al., 2013, 2015, 2016a; Provost et al., 2017; Luyten et al., 2020; Chua et
364 al., 2020; Korsiak et al., 2021). Higher levels of air pollution seemed to be adversely associated
365 with narrower retinal arterioles (CRAE) in most studies involving adults (Adar et al., 2010;
366 Louwies et al., 2013, 2016a), but not all (Louwies et al., 2015; Laeremans et al., 2018; Koch et
367 al., 2020). Regarding CRVE, previous research on air pollution exposure has yielded mixed
368 results. While some studies have found positive associations [i.e., wider retinal venules
369 (CRVE) with higher air pollution levels] (Adar et al., 2010; Louwies et al., 2015, 2016a), others
370 have observed no (Laeremans et al., 2018; Koch et al., 2020), or negative associations (Louwies
371 et al., 2013). The aforementioned study by Laeremans and colleagues (2018) was also part of
372 PASTA and used the same dataset as the current study. In our study, we evaluated associations
373 using BC which is considered a good proxy for traffic-related air pollution and important
374 cardiovascular risk factor. We assessed personal exposure monitoring to BC by portable
375 aethalometers, a validated tool that has been demonstrated to be accurate and reliable (Dons et

376 al., 2012). After accounting for BC, our effect estimates for CRAE remained nearly identical,
377 whereas those for CRVE showed a slight increase in strength.

378

379 The biological mechanisms that link air pollution's impact on the microcirculation are believed
380 to be, at least in part, associated with systemic inflammation (Brook et al., 2010; Stapleton et
381 al., 2011). Inflammation is critical in developing cardiovascular dysfunction (Alfaddagh et al.,
382 2020). Accumulating evidence suggests systemic inflammation to be associated with wider
383 retinal venules (Klein et al., 2006; Ikram et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2021), which could offer
384 additional support for our findings.

385

386 Furthermore, our findings for CRVE did not change after additionally accounting for blood
387 pressure, which could support the potentially independent role of CRVE in predicting
388 cardiovascular dysfunction, as suggested in prior research (Liu et al., 2019; Khanna and
389 Karamchandani, 2021). The correlation between CRAE and blood pressure is more well-
390 established. Smaller retinal arterioles are identified as both cause and consequence in the
391 pathophysiology of hypertension (Ikram et al., 2013; Wei et al., 2016; Farrah et al., 2020;
392 Hanssen et al., 2022) and may partly explain the loss of statistical significance in our main
393 model (M1) with CRAE. Considering the complex, two-way relationship between macro- and
394 microcirculation, it could be useful to further investigate any mediation effect by blood
395 pressure.

396

397 We consider our findings of significantly smaller retinal venules (CRVE) among individuals
398 exposed to higher levels of surrounding greenness biologically plausible. Higher levels of
399 greenspace have been beneficially associated with lower levels of several markers of
400 inflammation (Woo et al., 2009; Bijmens et al., 2015; Egorov et al., 2017; Martens and Nawrot,
401 2018; Yang et al., 2021; Iyer et al., 2022; Bikomeye et al., 2022; Mei et al., 2023). The
402 relationship between systemic inflammation and narrower retinal arterioles (CRAE) is less
403 established (Ikram et al., 2013; Rijks et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2021). Adverse changes in the
404 retinal arterioles appear to reflect structural damage and cardiovascular dysfunction at a more
405 advanced (i.e. severe) stage (Liu et al., 2019; Farrah et al., 2020; Hanssen et al., 2022).
406 Consequently, the lack of associations with CRAE could have been partially driven by our
407 study sample, consisting of healthy participants without prior cardiovascular conditions.

408

409 **Limitations**

410

411 The homogeneous distribution of our sample (i.e. highly educated healthy adults) may have
412 limited external validity and, thus, the generalizability of our findings to the entire population.
413 On this account, we could not explore potential effect modification for other individual
414 characteristics besides sex. Conversely, homogeneity and our repeated measures design could
415 favor the internal validity of our analyses. While our findings hold potential relevance for
416 public health, it remains essential to replicate this study using a larger sample representative of
417 the general population to validate them.

418 Further, our study accounted for individual spatiotemporal patterns by assessing surrounding
419 outdoor greenness at different locations (i.e. home and work/school), separately and combined
420 (i.e. daytime index). The latter was calculated based on self-reported (for work) and
421 approximated (for school) time use and activity patterns. Additionally, due to incomplete
422 information for a significant portion of participants, we were unable to investigate residential
423 mobility. Hence, potential exposure misclassification was a possibility. However, to improve

424 accuracy in exposure assessment, we matched the different time points of data collection to
425 their corresponding seasonal greenness (Markevych et al., 2017; Kumari et al., 2020).
426 To assess the retinal microvascular status, we analyzed individual fundus images for retinal
427 vessel metrics. This methodology has its limitations to differentiate between functional or
428 structural alterations of retinal vessels. Capturing images at multiple time points, as we did in
429 our study, may reveal a more dynamic functional response (Int Panis et al., 2017; Louwies et
430 al., 2016b, 2019; Streese et al., 2020; Gin et al., 2023). However, the response, including
431 remodeling, is expected to differ between arterioles and venules due to their distinct
432 composition and function. In contrast, Dynamic vessel analysis (DVA), which relies on
433 flickering light-induced dilatation of retinal arterioles and venules, is a promising approach,
434 and this technique should be used for a more in-depth investigation into microvascular function
435 (Hanssen et al., 2022).
436 Another potential limitation of our outcome assessment could be the fact that participants were
437 not given a vasodilatory stimulus to maximize vasodilation. While recognized as a valid
438 technique, the omission may have affected measurement precision (Hanssen et al., 2022).
439 Vasoconstriction is expected to be less of an issue in our study population, which mainly
440 consists of apparently healthy individuals. However, when replicating findings in a more
441 representative sample of the general population, considering vasodilation and vasoconstriction
442 may become more crucial.
443 Lastly, MONA REVA (VITO, Mol, Belgium; Khan et al., 2022), the software we used to
444 process the fundus images is semi-automatic and requires some manual interference to
445 determine the vessel widths. As a result, the outcomes might exhibit slight variations based on
446 the grading process. To limit intra-grader variability, the grader was blinded to participant
447 characteristics and different time points. Additionally, a standardized template was used to
448 ensure agreement in rating the batched participant images. Previous research has confirmed the
449 high reliability of fundus image processing, minimizing concerns about inter-grader variability
450 (De Boever et al., 2014).

451

452 **CONCLUSION**

453

454 This study across three cities in the south, center, and north of Europe assessed the relation
455 between surrounding outdoor greenness and the retinal microvasculature in healthy adults for
456 the first time. We consistently observed strongest associations between smaller retinal venules
457 and higher surrounding greenness at work/school. Our findings, if confirmed by future studies,
458 underscore the potential of greenspace, and possibly nature, to prevent adverse subclinical
459 changes in the cardiovascular system at early stages. We call for future research to confirm
460 these findings in different contextual settings and further explore the role of retinal vessel types
461 and potential mechanisms underlying this association.

462

463

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465

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476

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793 **Main tables and main figure**

794

795 **Table 1.** Characteristics of study participants (n=114). Descriptive statistics are presented as
 796 count (%) for categorical variables and median (interquartile range) for continuous variables.

797

Variable	Median (IQR)/n (%)
Individual level covariates	
Age	33 (12.8)
Women	61 (53.5%)
Nationality country of study	98 (86.0%)
Full-time employed	85 (74.6%)
Higher education	102 (89.5%)
Body mass index (BMI) ^a	22.7 (4.5)
Area level covariates^b	
Percentage of the population with low education	4.7 (8.0)
Percentage of the population with foreign origin	12.5 (27.1)

798 ^aBMI: objective body weight was not available for 3 participants; hence self-reported weight
 799 at the baseline survey was used to calculate BMI (kg/m²).

800 ^b Indicators of socioeconomic position at the neighbourhood level based on census-derived
 801 indicators.

802

803

804 **Table 2.** Outcome and exposure characteristics of the study participants by city. Descriptive statistics are presented as median (IQR) and the p-
 805 value of between-city comparison is obtained using the Kruskal–Wallis test.
 806

Variable	Full sample	Antwerp	Barcelona	London	p-value	
Retinal vessel metric (µm)						
Central retinal arteriolar equivalent (CRAE)	160.8 (19.3)	162.9 (17.6)	163.20 (18.4)	156.20 (14.7)	0.01	
Central retinal venular equivalent (CRVE)	235.6 (25.8)	232.2 (26.8)	241.35 (35.4)	235.50 (20.3)	0.05	
Surrounding greenness (seasonal NDVI)						
home	100m buffer	0.34 (0.23)	0.39 (0.21)	0.21 (0.06)	0.42 (0.17)	0.01
	300m buffer	0.35 (0.22)	0.42 (0.22)	0.22 (0.07)	0.41 (0.16)	0.01
	500m buffer	0.36 (0.21)	0.46 (0.23)	0.24 (0.08)	0.41 (0.15)	0.01
work/school	100m buffer	0.24 (0.16)	0.30 (0.20)	0.21 (0.09)	0.23 (0.18)	0.01
	300m buffer	0.27 (0.14)	0.31 (0.20)	0.25 (0.07)	0.27 (0.17)	0.01
	500m buffer	0.29 (0.14)	0.31 (0.24)	0.26 (0.08)	0.31 (0.17)	0.01

807
 808

809 **Table 3.** Adjusted beta coefficients (β) and 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) of the association between retinal vessel diameter (CRAE and
810 CRVE) and one interquartile increase (IQR) in 100m, 300m, and 500m buffers for surrounding greenness (seasonal NDVI) by location.
811

		CRAE		CRVE	
		Model 1 ^a	Model 2 ^b	Model 1 ^a	Model 2 ^b
seasonal NDVI	IQR	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)
home					
100m buffer	0.23	-2.57 (-5.68,0.53)	-1.19 (-3.88,1.49)	-3.57 (-7.69,0.54)	-1.83 (-5.47,1.81)
300m buffer	0.22	-2.99 (-6.33,0.36)	-1.14 (-4.02,1.73)	-4.84 (-9.31,-0.37)	-2.82 (-6.73,1.10)
500m buffer	0.21	-2.36 (-5.56,0.83)	-0.95 (-3.69,1.79)	-3.94 (-8.20,0.33)	-2.34 (-6.07,1.39)
work/school					
100m buffer	0.16	-0.19 (-2.53,2.15)	0.54 (-1.43,2.51)	-1.63 (-4.79,1.53)	-1.78 (-4.49,0.92)
300m buffer	0.14	-1.74 (-3.83,0.35)	-0.18 (-1.97,1.60)	-3.85 (-6.67,-1.03)	-3.04 (-5.46,-0.63)
500m buffer	0.14	-2.38 (-4.56,-0.21)	-0.34 (-2.21,1.54)	-5.11 (-8.04,-2.18)	-3.89 (-6.40,-1.37)

812 Note: statistically significant beta coefficients are indicated in bold text (p-value < 0.05). Number of participants = 114 and number of repeated
813 observations = 303.

814 ^aModel 1 (M1) adjusted for individual sociodemographic covariates (age, sex, BMI (kg/m²), nationality, education level, employment status),
815 and area-level covariates (low-educated and foreign origin, temperature, relative humidity), with participant ID as random effect and city as
816 fixed effect.

817 ^bModel 2 (M2) M1 additionally adjusted for fellow vessel diameter.

818

819

820 **Figure 1.** Adjusted beta coefficients (β) and 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) of the
 821 association between retinal vessel diameter (CRAE and CRVE) and one interquartile increase
 822 (IQR) in 300m buffer seasonal NDVI by location and by sex.
 823

824
 825
 826 Note: Model 1 (M1; *circle*) adjusted for individual sociodemographic covariates (age, sex, BMI
 827 (kg/m^2), nationality, education level, employment status), and area-level covariates (low-
 828 educated and foreign origin, temperature, relative humidity), with participant ID as random
 829 effect and city as a fixed effect. Model 2 (M2; *triangle*) M1 additionally adjusted for fellow
 830 vessel diameter. Number of participants = 114 and number of repeated observations = 303 of
 831 which 46% men and 54% women.
 832

833 **Supplementary material**

834

835 S1. Additional information on the exposure assessment: seasonal and annual surrounding
836 greenness (NDVI and MSAVI2), ambient air pollution (BC), temperature and relative
837 humidity.

838

839 S1.1 surrounding greenness

840 Surrounding greenness was characterized using two vegetation indices (VI): the Normalized
841 Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) (Tucker, 1979) and the Modified Soil-adjusted
842 Vegetation Index 2 (MSAVI2) (Huete, 1988; Qi et al., 1994a,b). NDVI, which is most widely
843 used, is derived from the ratio of visible (RED) and near infrared (NIR) light bands
844 [$NDVI = (NIR - RED) / (NIR + RED)$] representing the difference of land surface reflectance
845 (Tucker, 1979). MSAVI2 additionally includes a factor to correct for soil brightness and may
846 be more accurate in areas where vegetation is low, such as urban areas, prairies, or deserts (Qi
847 et al., 1994b). Values of both vegetation indices range between - 1 and + 1, where values
848 closest to +1 represent highest photosynthetically active vegetation. Both vegetation indices
849 were retrieved from atmospherically corrected cloud-free satellite images from Landsat 8 at
850 spatial resolution of 30 m X 30 m (Gorelick et al., 2017).

851 Surrounding greenness was assigned as both seasonal and annual exposure. Time-varying
852 seasonal greenness included matching of the different data collection time points to its
853 corresponding meteorological season (northern hemisphere, i.e. *winter*: 1 December - 28/29
854 February; *spring*: 1 March - 31 May; *summer*: 1 June - 31 August; *autumn*: 1 September - 30
855 November). Measurement campaigns for the PASTA add-on study took place from 02-2015
856 until 03-2016 (Antwerp: 02-2015 until 03-2016; Barcelona: 03-2015 until 03-2016; London:
857 04-2015 until 03-2016). A total of 16 satellite images were retrieved for both NDVI and
858 MSAVI2 (Antwerp: 6; Barcelona: 5; London: 5).

859 Each seasonal satellite image was composed of the 'greenest' available pixels available within
860 the corresponding predefined date range. The aforementioned compilation was generated using
861 an algorithm that selected the highest positive values within each grid cell (Gorelick et al.,
862 2017). The aforementioned approach was also applied to gather annual greenness exposure,
863 whereby satellite imagery was collected over the entire study period for NDVI only (i.e. one
864 satellite image per city; $n=3$).

865 We calculated the average index value around the geocoded address at each location and for
866 each time point across circular Euclidean buffers of 100 m, 300 m and 500 m for both NDVI
867 and MSAVI2, resulting for each participant in 36 seasonal greenness measures [i.e. 3 (seasons)
868 x 2 (vegetation indices) x 2 (locations) x 3 (buffers)] and 6 annual measures [i.e. 1 (vegetation
869 index) x 2 (locations) x 3 (buffers)]. To prevent the averaging out of VI values, negative values
870 representing water surfaces were coded to zero prior to buffer calculation (Klomp maker et al.,
871 2018).

872 We used Google Earth Engine (GEE) (Gorelick et al., 2017; Markevych et al., 2017) to obtain
873 satellite imagery by city. Examples of applied scripts and procedures for each vegetation index
874 separately can be found in prior publications (Bauwelinck et al. 2020; 2021).

875

876

877 S1.2 ambient air pollution, temperature and relative humidity

878 Air pollution data was available by personal exposure measurements. Black carbon (BC)
879 concentrations were obtained by microAeth wearable sensors (model AE51, Aethlabs, San
880 Francisco, California, USA) as weekly averages matching the time point of health
881 measurement. Temperature and relative humidity were averaged weekly corresponding to each
882 time point using data from fixed central monitoring stations in each city (Avila-Palencia et al.,
883 2019).

884

885 S2. Additional information on the assessment of blood pressure.
886 Blood pressure levels were measured using a fully automatic blood pressure monitor (model
887 M10-IT, Omron, Japan). We adhered to a standardized blood pressure measurement protocol
888 based on the guidelines provided by the European Society of Hypertension (O'Brien et al.,
889 2013). At each of the three data collection visits, after a 10-min period of rest, blood pressure
890 was assessed five times with 2-min intervals using the participant's non-dominant arm.
891 Measurements were carried out by trained staff from each participating research center.
892 Available blood pressure measures included: systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood
893 pressure (DBP). In our analyses we used the mean of the last three measurements collected in
894 each visit. A measurement session was considered valid if at least three single measurements
895 had been collected, otherwise it was excluded from further analysis. In our models we adjusted
896 for the mean arterial blood pressure (MAP; [MAP = (2/3 * DBP) + (1/3 * SBP)]).
897

Table S1. Descriptive characteristics of the study participants by city.

Variable	Full sample	Antwerp	Barcelona	London	p-value	
<i>n participants</i>	114	40	39	35		
<i>n repeated observations</i>	303	114	93	96		
Individual level covariates						
Age	33 (12.8)	36 (15.3)	34 (12.5)	31 (9.0)	0.17	
Women	61 (53.5%)	18 (45.0%)	23 (59.0%)	20 (57.1%)	0.40	
Nationality country of study	98 (86.0%)	39 (97.5%)	33 (84.6%)	26 (74.3%)	0.01	
Full-time employed	85 (74.6%)	32 (80.0%)	32 (82.1%)	21 (60.0%)	0.06	
Higher education	102 (89.5%)	36 (90.0%)	35 (89.7%)	31 (88.6%)	0.99	
Body mass index (BMI) ^a , kg/m ²	22.7 (4.5)	22.6 (3.9)	22.7 (4.6)	23.3 (4.9)	0.92	
Systolic blood pressure (SBP), mmHg	103.0 (16.5)	104.3 (15.7)	100.3 (17.3)	103.3 (14.8)	0.10	
Diastolic blood pressure (DBP), mmHg	68.7 (10.7)	66.0 (10.0)	68.0 (10.7)	71.5 (9.9)	0.01	
Mean arterial pressure (MAP) ^b , mmHg	79.9 (11.9)	79.3 (12.1)	78.3 (11.7)	82.2 (11.0)	0.01	
Area level covariates^c						
Percentage of population with low education	4.7 (8.0)	1.6 (1.3)	5.4 (3.0)	11.3 (5.9)	0.01	
Percentage of population with foreign origin	12.5 (27.1)	4.9 (0.0)	12.3 (7.5)	38.1 (14.5)	0.01	
Retinal vessel metric (µm)						
Central retinal arteriolar equivalent (CRAE)	160.79 (19.28)	162.92 (17.62)	163.20 (18.37)	156.20 (14.68)	0.01	
Central retinal venular equivalent (CRVE)	235.56 (25.82)	232.23 (26.77)	241.35 (35.38)	235.50 (20.30)	0.05	
Exposure measures						
<i>Surrounding greenness (seasonal NDVI)</i>						
home	100m buffer	0.34 (0.23)	0.39 (0.21)	0.21 (0.06)	0.42 (0.17)	0.01
	300m buffer	0.35 (0.22)	0.42 (0.22)	0.22 (0.07)	0.41 (0.16)	0.01
	500m buffer	0.36 (0.21)	0.46 (0.23)	0.24 (0.08)	0.41 (0.15)	0.01
work/school	100m buffer	0.24 (0.16)	0.30 (0.20)	0.21 (0.09)	0.23 (0.18)	0.01
	300m buffer	0.27 (0.14)	0.31 (0.20)	0.25 (0.07)	0.27 (0.17)	0.01
	500m buffer	0.29 (0.14)	0.31 (0.24)	0.26 (0.08)	0.31 (0.17)	0.01
<i>Ambient air pollution (µg/m³)</i>						

Black carbon (BC) ^d	1.34 (0.73)	1.22 (0.67)	1.56 (0.65)	1.26 (0.63)	0.01
<i>Other</i>					
Temperature, °C	14 (8.61)	12.16 (7.07)	19.04 (10.40)	13.56 (8.66)	0.01
Relative humidity	74 (17.00)	84.0 (17.00)	69.0 (12.00)	74.5 (16.00)	0.01

899 Note: descriptive statistics are presented as count (%) for categorical variables and as median (interquartile range) for continuous variables. P-
900 value of between-city comparison is obtained using the Fisher's exact test for categorical variables and the Kruskal–Wallis test for continuous
901 variables.

902 ^aBMI: objective body weight not available for 3 participants, hence self-reported weight at time of baseline survey was used to calculate BMI.

903 ^bMAP: calculated with the following formula; $MAP = (2/3 * DBP) + (1/3 * SBP)$

904 ^c Indicators of socioeconomic position at neighbourhood level based on census-derived indicators.

905 ^dBC: personal exposure obtained by microAeth wearable sensors

906

907

908 **Table S2.** Spearman correlations for surrounding greenness (seasonal NDVI), ambient air pollution (BC), temperature and relative humidity at
 909 home and work/school
 910

		seasonal NDVI						BC	temperature	relative humidity	
		home			work/school						
		100m	300m	500m	100m	300m	500m				
seasonal NDVI	home	100m	1.00	0.93	0.88	0.22	0.21	0.22	-0.24	-0.31	0.25
		300m	0.93	1.00	0.98	0.27	0.29	0.30	-0.21	-0.31	0.24
		500m	0.88	0.98	1.00	0.29	0.31	0.32	-0.21	-0.31	0.24
	work/school	100m	0.22	0.27	0.29	1.00	0.82	0.75	-0.03	-0.04	0.10
		300m	0.21	0.29	0.31	0.82	1.00	0.96	-0.03	-0.02	0.11
		500m	0.22	0.30	0.32	0.75	0.96	1.00	-0.05	-0.03	0.11
BC		-0.24	-0.21	-0.21	-0.03	-0.03	-0.05	1.00	0.11	0.06	
temperature		-0.31	-0.31	-0.31	-0.04	-0.02	-0.03	0.11	1.00	-0.57	
relative humidity		0.25	0.24	0.24	0.10	0.11	0.11	0.06	-0.57	1.00	

911

912 **Table S3.** Spearman correlations for surrounding greenness (seasonal NDVI and MSAVI2 and annual NDVI) at home and work/school

			home										work/school										
			100m			300m			500m				100m			300m			500m				
			seasonal		annual	seasonal		annual	seasonal		annual	seasonal		annual	seasonal		annual	seasonal		annual			
			NDVI	MSAVI2	NDVI	NDVI	MSAVI2	NDVI	NDVI	MSAVI2	NDVI	NDVI	MSAVI2	NDVI	NDVI	MSAVI2	NDVI	NDVI	MSAVI2	NDVI	NDVI	MSAVI2	NDVI
home	100m	seasonal	NDVI	1.00	0.99	0.94	0.93	0.92	0.87	0.88	0.88	0.82	0.22	0.23	0.17	0.21	0.21	0.17	0.22	0.23	0.14		
			MSAVI2	0.99	1.00	0.93	0.93	0.93	0.87	0.89	0.89	0.82	0.22	0.23	0.17	0.21	0.22	0.17	0.23	0.24	0.14		
	300m	seasonal	NDVI	0.93	0.93	0.89	1.00	1.00	0.96	0.98	0.97	0.92	0.27	0.28	0.23	0.29	0.29	0.26	0.30	0.31	0.22		
			MSAVI2	0.92	0.93	0.88	1.00	1.00	0.95	0.98	0.98	0.93	0.27	0.28	0.22	0.29	0.29	0.26	0.30	0.31	0.22		
	500m	seasonal	NDVI	0.88	0.89	0.85	0.98	0.98	0.94	1.00	1.00	0.96	0.29	0.30	0.26	0.31	0.31	0.30	0.32	0.33	0.26		
			MSAVI2	0.88	0.89	0.84	0.97	0.98	0.94	1.00	1.00	0.95	0.29	0.30	0.25	0.31	0.32	0.29	0.32	0.34	0.26		
work/school	100m	seasonal	NDVI	0.22	0.22	0.20	0.27	0.27	0.24	0.29	0.29	0.25	1.00	1.00	0.90	0.82	0.84	0.74	0.75	0.77	0.66		
			MSAVI2	0.23	0.23	0.21	0.28	0.28	0.24	0.30	0.30	0.25	1.00	1.00	0.89	0.82	0.84	0.74	0.75	0.77	0.65		
	300m	seasonal	NDVI	0.21	0.21	0.16	0.29	0.29	0.23	0.31	0.31	0.25	0.82	0.82	0.73	1.00	1.00	0.89	0.96	0.96	0.87		
			MSAVI2	0.21	0.22	0.16	0.29	0.29	0.24	0.31	0.32	0.25	0.84	0.84	0.74	1.00	1.00	0.89	0.95	0.96	0.86		
	500m	seasonal	NDVI	0.22	0.23	0.17	0.30	0.30	0.24	0.32	0.32	0.26	0.75	0.75	0.66	0.96	0.95	0.84	1.00	0.99	0.90		
			MSAVI2	0.23	0.24	0.17	0.31	0.31	0.25	0.33	0.34	0.27	0.77	0.77	0.67	0.96	0.96	0.84	0.99	1.00	0.88		
annual	NDVI	0.17	0.17	0.21	0.23	0.22	0.25	0.26	0.25	0.27	0.90	0.89	1.00	0.73	0.74	0.81	0.66	0.67	0.71				
		0.17	0.17	0.20	0.26	0.26	0.28	0.30	0.29	0.31	0.74	0.74	0.81	0.89	0.89	1.00	0.84	0.84	0.95				
annual	NDVI	0.14	0.14	0.16	0.22	0.22	0.24	0.26	0.26	0.27	0.66	0.65	0.71	0.87	0.86	0.95	0.90	0.88	1.00				
		0.14	0.14	0.16	0.22	0.22	0.24	0.26	0.26	0.27	0.66	0.65	0.71	0.87	0.86	0.95	0.90	0.88	1.00				

913
914

915 **Table S4.** Adjusted beta coefficients (β) and 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) of the association between retinal vessel diameter (CRAE and
 916 CRVE) and one interquartile increase (IQR) in 100m, 300m and 500m buffers surrounding greenness (NDVI and MSAVI2) by location (home,
 917 work/school, and daytime index).

			CRAE				CRVE	
				Model 1 ^a	Model 2 ^b	Model 1 ^a	Model 2 ^b	
			IQR	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	
<i>home</i>								
100m buffer	seasonal	NDVI	0.23	-2.57 (-5.68,0.53)	-1.19 (-3.88,1.49)	-3.57 (-7.69,0.54)	-1.83 (-5.47,1.81)	
		MSAVI2	0.26	-1.84 (-4.66,0.97)	-0.99 (-3.47,1.48)	-2.33 (-6.02,1.37)	-1.12 (-4.43,2.19)	
300m buffer	seasonal	NDVI	0.22	-2.99 (-6.33,0.36)	-1.14 (-4.02,1.73)	-4.84 (-9.31,-0.37)	-2.82 (-6.73,1.10)	
		MSAVI2	0.24	-2.55 (-5.84,0.73)	-0.83 (-3.70,2.04)	-4.62 (-8.96,-0.28)	-2.94 (-6.79,0.91)	
500m buffer	seasonal	NDVI	0.21	-2.36 (-5.56,0.83)	-0.95 (-3.69,1.79)	-3.94 (-8.19,0.33)	-2.34 (-6.07,1.39)	
		MSAVI2	0.23	-2.06 (-5.14,1.03)	-0.84 (-3.52,1.84)	-3.43 (-7.50,0.65)	-2.08 (-5.69,1.52)	
<i>work/school</i>								
100m buffer	seasonal	NDVI	0.16	-0.19 (-2.53,2.15)	0.54 (-1.43,2.51)	-1.63 (-4.79,1.53)	-1.78 (-4.49,0.92)	
		MSAVI2	0.19	-0.56 (-2.86,1.75)	0.38 (-1.58,2.34)	-2.13 (-5.21,0.95)	-1.93 (-4.60,0.73)	
300m buffer	seasonal	NDVI	0.14	-1.74 (-3.83,0.35)	-0.18 (-1.97,1.60)	-3.85 (-6.67,-1.03)	-3.04 (-5.46,-0.63)	
		MSAVI2	0.16	-2.11 (-4.31,0.09)	-0.39 (-2.29,1.50)	-4.25 (-7.20,-1.30)	-3.17 (-5.73,-0.61)	
500m buffer	seasonal	NDVI	0.14	-2.38 (-4.56,-0.21)	-0.34 (-2.21,1.54)	-5.11 (-8.04,-2.18)	-3.89 (-6.40,-1.37)	
		MSAVI2	0.17	-2.71 (-5.05,-0.38)	-0.47 (-2.50,1.56)	-5.58 (-8.70,-2.47)	-4.16 (-6.87,-1.45)	
<i>daytime index</i>								
100m buffer	seasonal	NDVI	0.17	-1.92 (-4.80,0.96)	-0.49 (-3.00,2.01)	-3.47 (-7.29,0.34)	-2.43 (-5.79,0.94)	
		MSAVI2	0.19	-1.58 (-4.23,1.06)	-0.44 (-2.77,1.89)	-2.82 (-6.29,0.65)	-1.97 (-5.07,1.13)	
300m buffer	seasonal	NDVI	0.15	-2.80 (-5.54,-0.07)	-0.73 (-3.12,1.65)	-5.24 (-8.88,-1.61)	-3.74 (-6.93,-0.54)	
		MSAVI2	0.17	-2.61 (-5.24,0.01)	-0.65 (-2.97,1.67)	-5.00 (-8.46,-1.54)	-3.61 (-6.69,-0.54)	
500m buffer	seasonal	NDVI	0.16	-3.03 (-5.86,-0.20)	-0.77 (-3.25,1.70)	-5.79 (-9.55,-2.04)	-4.18 (-7.49,-0.87)	
		MSAVI2	0.17	-2.81 (-5.53,-0.10)	-0.73 (-3.13,1.67)	-5.33 (-8.91,-1.75)	-3.87 (-7.10,-0.69)	

918 Note: statistically significant beta coefficients are indicated in bold text (p-value < 0.05). Number of participants = 114 and number of repeated observations =
 919 303.

920 ^aModel 1 (M1) adjusted for individual sociodemographic covariates (age, sex, BMI (kg/m²), nationality, education level, employment status), and area-level
921 covariates (low-educated and foreign origin, temperature, relative humidity), with participant ID as random effect and city as fixed effect.
922 ^bModel 2 (M2) M1 additionally adjusted for fellow vessel diameter.

923 **Table S5.** Adjusted beta coefficients (β) and 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) of the association between retinal vessel diameter (CRAE and
 924 CRVE) and one interquartile increase (IQR) in 100m, 300m and 500m buffers surrounding greenness (seasonal and annual NDVI) by location
 925 (home, work/school, and daytime index).

			CRAE				CRVE	
				Model 1 ^a	Model 2 ^b	Model 1 ^a	Model 2 ^b	
			IQR	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	
<i>home</i>								
100m buffer	NDVI	seasonal	0.23	-2.57 (-5.68,0.53)	-1.19 (-3.88,1.49)	-3.57 (-7.69,0.54)	-1.83 (-5.47,1.81)	
		annual	0.21	-3.40 (-8.49,1.70)	-2.01 (-5.92,1.90)	-3.61 (-11.08,3.87)	-1.26 (-7.13,4.60)	
300m buffer	NDVI	seasonal	0.22	-2.99 (-6.33,0.36)	-1.14 (-4.02,1.73)	-4.84 (-9.31,-0.37)	-2.82 (-6.73,1.10)	
		annual	0.22	-3.24 (-8.47,2.27)	-1.51 (-5.74,2.73)	-4.50 (-12.55,3.55)	-2.28 (-8.59,4.03)	
500m buffer	NDVI	seasonal	0.21	-2.36 (-5.56,0.83)	-0.95 (-3.69,1.79)	-3.94 (-8.19,0.33)	-2.34 (-6.07,1.39)	
		annual	0.23	-3.46 (-9.06,2.14)	-1.78 (-6.09,2.53)	-4.38 (-12.58,3.81)	-2.01 (-8.43,4.42)	
<i>work/school</i>								
100m buffer	NDVI	seasonal	0.16	-0.19 (-2.53,2.15)	0.54 (-1.43,2.51)	-1.63 (-4.79,1.53)	-1.78 (-4.49,0.92)	
		annual	0.17	-0.10 (-3.73,3.53)	0.87 (-1.91,3.64)	-2.54 (-7.82,2.73)	-2.47 (-6.58,1.63)	
300m buffer	NDVI	seasonal	0.14	-1.74 (-3.83,0.35)	-0.18 (-1.97,1.60)	-3.85 (-6.67,-1.03)	-3.04 (-5.46,-0.63)	
		annual	0.13	-2.78 (-5.65,0.08)	-0.37 (-2.63,1.90)	-6.30 (-10.38,-2.21)	-4.39 (-7.63,-1.15)	
500m buffer	NDVI	seasonal	0.14	-2.38 (-4.56,-0.21)	-0.34 (-2.21,1.54)	-5.11 (-8.04,-2.18)	-3.89 (-6.40,-1.37)	
		annual	0.14	-3.29 (-6.30,-0.27)	-0.30 (-2.72,2.11)	-7.77 (-12.02,-3.51)	-5.54 (-8.93,-2.15)	
<i>daytime index</i>								
100m buffer	NDVI	seasonal	0.17	-1.92 (-4.80,0.96)	-0.49 (-3.00,2.01)	-3.47 (-7.29,0.34)	-2.43 (-5.79,0.94)	
		annual	0.15	-2.51 (-7.03,2.02)	-0.76 (-4.25,2.72)	-4.57 (-11.16,2.02)	-2.84 (-8.01,2.32)	
300m buffer	NDVI	seasonal	0.15	-2.80 (-5.54,-0.07)	-0.73 (-3.12,1.65)	-5.24 (-8.88,-1.61)	-3.74 (-6.93,-0.54)	
		annual	0.16	-4.90 (-9.67,-0.14)	-1.31 (-5.08,2.45)	-9.40 (-16.27,-2.53)	-6.06 (-11.52,-0.60)	
500m buffer	NDVI	seasonal	0.16	-3.03 (-5.86,-0.20)	-0.77 (-3.25,1.70)	-5.79 (-9.55,-2.04)	-4.18 (-7.49,-0.87)	
		annual	0.15	-5.06 (-9.61,-0.52)	-1.35 (-4.95,2.26)	-9.75 (-16.27,-3.22)	-6.32 (-11.53,-1.11)	

926 Note: statistically significant beta coefficients are indicated in bold text (p-value < 0.05). Number of participants = 114 and number of repeated observations =
 927 303.

928 ^aModel 1 (M1) adjusted for individual sociodemographic covariates (age, sex, BMI (kg/m²), nationality, education level, employment status), and area-level
929 covariates (low-educated and foreign origin, temperature, relative humidity), with participant ID as random effect and city as fixed effect.
930 ^bModel 2 (M2) M1 additionally adjusted for fellow vessel diameter.

931 **Table S6.** Adjusted beta coefficients $s(\beta)$ and 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) of the association between retinal vessel diameter (CRAE and
 932 CRVE) and one interquartile increase (IQR) in surrounding greenness (seasonal NDVI; 100m, 300m and 500m buffers) by location (home and
 933 work/school) after further adjustment for population density.

		CRAE		CRVE		
		Main models	Further adjusted for population density	Main models	Further adjusted for population density	
seasonal NDVI	IQR	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	
<i>home</i>						
100m buffer	0.23	M1 ^a	-2.57 (-5.68,0.53)	-2.98 (-6.13,0.17)	-3.57 (-7.69,0.54)	-3.38 (-7.55,0.80)
		M2 ^b	-1.19 (-3.88,1.49)	-1.82 (-4.55,0.90)	-1.83 (-5.47,1.81)	-1.25 (-4.95,2.45)
300m buffer	0.22	M1 ^a	-2.99 (-6.33,0.36)	-3.75 (-7.21,-0.28)	-4.84 (-9.30,-0.37)	-4.66 (-9.27,-0.05)
		M2 ^b	-1.14 (-4.02,1.73)	-2.20 (-5.18,0.78)	-2.82 (-6.73,1.10)	-2.01 (-6.09,2.06)
500m buffer	0.21	M1 ^a	-2.36 (-5.56,0.83)	-3.03 (-6.34,0.27)	-3.94 (-8.20,0.33)	-3.72 (-8.11,0.68)
		M2 ^b	-0.95 (-3.69,1.77)	-1.94 (-4.78,0.89)	-2.34 (-6.07,1.39)	-1.56 (-5.43,2.31)
<i>work/school</i>						
100m buffer	0.16	M1 ^a	-0.19 (-2.53,2.15)	-0.16 (-2.50,2.17)	-1.64 (-4.79,1.53)	-1.67 (-4.83,1.49)
		M2 ^b	0.54 (-1.43,2.51)	0.60 (-1.35,2.55)	-1.78 (-4.49,0.92)	-1.86 (-4.55,0.83)
300m buffer	0.14	M1 ^a	-1.74 (-3.83,0.35)	-1.80 (-3.88,0.29)	-3.85 (-6.67,-1.03)	-3.81 (-6.63,-1.00)
		M2 ^b	-0.18 (-1.97,1.59)	-0.25 (-2.01,1.52)	-3.04 (-5.46,-0.63)	-2.97 (-5.37,-0.56)
500m buffer	0.14	M1 ^a	-2.38 (-4.56,-0.21)	-2.43 (-4.60,-0.25)	-5.11 (-8.04,-2.18)	-5.08 (-8.01,-2.16)
		M2 ^b	-0.34 (-2.21,1.54)	-0.38 (-2.24,1.48)	-3.89 (-6.40,-1.37)	-3.82 (-6.33,-1.32)

934 Note: statistically significant beta coefficients are indicated in bold text (p-value < 0.05). Number of participants = 114 and number of repeated
 935 observations = 303.

936 ^aModel 1 (M1) adjusted for individual sociodemographic covariates (age, sex, BMI (kg/m²), nationality, education level, employment status),
 937 and area-level covariates (low-educated and foreign origin, temperature, relative humidity), with participant ID as random effect and city as
 938 fixed effect.

939 ^bModel 2 (M2) M1 additionally adjusted for fellow vessel diameter.

940 **Table S7.** Adjusted beta coefficients $s(\beta)$ and 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) of the association between retinal vessel diameter (CRAE and
 941 CRVE) and one interquartile increase (IQR) in surrounding greenness (seasonal NDVI; 100m, 300m and 500m buffers) by location (home and
 942 work/school) for nonmovers.

			CRAE		CRVE	
			Main models	Main models subset nonmovers	Main models	Main models subset nonmovers
<i>n participants</i>			114	56	114	56
<i>n repeated observations</i>			303	156	303	156
seasonal NDVI	IQR		β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)
<i>home</i>						
100m buffer	0.23	M1 ^a	-2.57 (-5.68,0.53)	-4.67 (-9.36,0.02)	-3.57 (-7.69,0.54)	-3.50 (-9.87,2.87)
		M2 ^b	-1.19 (-3.88,1.49)	-3.15 (-7.10,0.79)	-1.83 (-5.47,1.81)	-0.43 (-5.88,5.02)
300m buffer	0.22	M1 ^a	-2.99 (-6.33,0.36)	-4.49 (-9.17,0.19)	-4.84 (-9.30,-0.37)	-4.90 (-11.27,1.46)
		M2 ^b	-1.14 (-4.02,1.73)	-2.44 (-6.40,1.51)	-2.82 (-6.73,1.10)	-2.03 (-7.47,3.40)
500m buffer	0.21	M1 ^a	-2.36 (-5.56,0.83)	-3.80 (-8.21,0.60)	-3.94 (-8.20,0.33)	-4.46 (-10.43,1.50)
		M2 ^b	-0.95 (-3.69,1.77)	-1.96 (-5.68,1.76)	-2.34 (-6.07,1.39)	-2.11 (-7.19,2.97)
<i>work/school</i>						
100m buffer	0.16	M1 ^a	-0.19 (-2.53,2.15)	-1.21 (-4.55,2.14)	-1.64 (-4.79,1.53)	-2.66 (-7.15,1.83)
		M2 ^b	0.54 (-1.43,2.51)	0.11 (-2.71,2.92)	-1.78 (-4.49,0.92)	-2.22 (-6.01,1.56)
300m buffer	0.14	M1 ^a	-1.74 (-3.83,0.35)	-2.45 (-5.46,0.55)	-3.85 (-6.67,-1.03)	-5.04 (-9.06,-1.01)
		M2 ^b	-0.18 (-1.97,1.59)	-0.27 (-2.86,2.33)	-3.04 (-5.46,-0.63)	-3.62 (-7.04,-0.19)
500m buffer	0.14	M1 ^a	-2.38 (-4.56,-0.21)	-2.82 (-5.98,0.34)	-5.11 (-8.04,-2.18)	-6.00 (-10.22,-1.78)
		M2 ^b	-0.34 (-2.21,1.54)	-0.25 (-2.99,2.48)	-3.89 (-6.40,-1.37)	-4.31 (-7.91,-0.72)

943 Note: statistically significant beta coefficients are indicated in bold text (p-value < 0.05).

944 ^aModel 1 (M1) adjusted for individual sociodemographic covariates (age, sex, BMI (kg/m²), nationality, education level, employment status),
 945 and area-level covariates (low-educated and foreign origin, temperature, relative humidity), with participant ID as random effect and city as
 946 fixed effect.

947 ^bModel 2 (M2) M1 additionally adjusted for fellow vessel diameter.

948 **Table S8.** Adjusted beta coefficients (β) and 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) of the association between retinal vessel diameter (CRAE and
 949 CRVE) and one interquartile increase (IQR) in surrounding greenness (seasonal NDVI; 100m, 300m and 500m buffers) by location (home and
 950 work/school) after further adjustment for city as random effect, ambient air pollution (BC), or mean arterial pressure (MAP).

		CRAE				
		Main models	Further adjusted for		City as random effect	
			BC	MAP		
seasonal NDVI	IQR	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	
<i>home</i>						
100m buffer	0.23	M1 ^a	-2.57 (-5.68,0.53)	-2.57 (-5.68,0.53)	-2.39 (-5.39,0.59)	-2.18 (-4.91,0.54)
		M2 ^b	-1.19 (-3.88,1.49)	-1.18 (-3.87,1.51)	-1.11 (-3.71,1.49)	-0.58 (-2.89,1.74)
300m buffer	0.22	M1 ^a	-2.99 (-6.33,0.36)	-2.99 (-6.36,0.36)	-2.56 (-5.78,0.66)	-2.34 (-5.21,0.54)
		M2 ^b	-1.14 (-4.02,1.73)	-1.12 (-4.00,1.77)	-0.96 (-3.72,1.81)	-0.37 (-2.78,2.05)
500m buffer	0.21	M1 ^a	-2.36 (-5.56,0.83)	-2.37 (-5.57,0.84)	-1.92 (-4.99,1.16)	-1.89 (-4.66,0.87)
		M2 ^b	-0.95 (-3.69,1.77)	-0.93 (-3.67,1.82)	-0.75 (-3.39,1.89)	-0.26 (-2.58,2.06)
<i>work/school</i>						
100m buffer	0.16	M1 ^a	-0.19 (-2.53,2.15)	-0.17 (-2.53,2.18)	0.04 (-2.20,2.27)	-0.22 (-2.48,2.05)
		M2 ^b	0.54 (-1.43,2.51)	0.58 (-1.40,2.56)	0.78 (-1.11,2.66)	0.68 (-1.21,2.58)
300m buffer	0.14	M1 ^a	-1.74 (-3.83,0.35)	-1.75 (-3.85,0.35)	-1.51 (-3.51,0.49)	-1.61 (-3.64,0.42)
		M2 ^b	-0.18 (-1.97,1.59)	-0.16 (-1.95,1.63)	-0.02 (-1.73,1.69)	0.04 (-1.69,1.77)
500m buffer	0.14	M1 ^a	-2.38 (-4.56,-0.21)	-2.39 (-4.59,-0.21)	-1.98 (-4.07,0.11)	-2.19 (-4.30,-0.08)
		M2 ^b	-0.34 (-2.21,1.54)	-0.32 (-2.20,1.57)	-0.07 (-1.87,1.72)	-0.08 (-1.89,1.74)

951 Note: statistically significant beta coefficients are indicated in bold text (p-value < 0.05). Number of participants = 114 and number of repeated
 952 observations = 303.

953 ^aModel 1 (M1) adjusted for individual sociodemographic covariates (age, sex, BMI (kg/m²), nationality, education level, employment status),
 954 and area-level covariates (low-educated and foreign origin, temperature, relative humidity), with participant ID as random effect and city as
 955 fixed effect.

956 ^bModel 2 (M2) M1 additionally adjusted for fellow vessel diameter.
 957

958 **Table S8.** (Continued). Adjusted beta coefficients (β) and 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) of the association between retinal vessel diameter
 959 (CRAE and CRVE) and one interquartile increase (IQR) in surrounding greenness (seasonal NDVI; 100m, 300m and 500m buffers) by location
 960 (home and work/school) after further adjustment for city as random effect, ambient air pollution (BC), or mean arterial pressure (MAP).

		CRVE				
		Main models	Further adjusted for		City as random effect	
			BC	MAP		
seasonal NDVI	IQR	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	
<i>home</i>						
100m buffer	0.23	M1 ^a	-3.57 (-7.69,0.54)	-3.63 (-7.76,0.49)	-3.46 (-7.53,0.61)	-3.90 (-7.59,-0.21)
		M2 ^b	-1.83 (-5.47,1.81)	-1.89 (-5.53,1.76)	-1.83 (-5.47,1.81)	-2.49 (-5.68,0.69)
300m buffer	0.22	M1 ^a	-4.84 (-9.30,-0.37)	-4.97 (-9.46,-0.48)	-4.49 (-8.91,-0.06)	-4.89 (-8.79,-0.99)
		M2 ^b	-2.82 (-6.73,1.10)	-2.95 (-6.87,0.99)	-2.80 (-6.72,1.11)	-3.34 (-6.67,-0.01)
500m buffer	0.21	M1 ^a	-3.94 (-8.20,0.33)	-4.04 (-8.32,0.24)	-3.54 (-7.76,0.69)	-4.17 (-7.93,-0.42)
		M2 ^b	-2.34 (-6.07,1.39)	-2.45 (-6.19,1.29)	-2.32 (-6.05,1.42)	-2.94 (-6.14,0.27)
<i>work/school</i>						
100m buffer	0.16	M1 ^a	-1.64 (-4.79,1.53)	-1.73 (-4.91,1.46)	-1.51 (-4.63,1.62)	-2.01 (-5.07,1.06)
		M2 ^b	-1.78 (-4.49,0.92)	-1.89 (-4.61,0.83)	-1.76 (-4.47,0.95)	-2.18 (-4.79,0.44)
300m buffer	0.14	M1 ^a	-3.85 (-6.67,-1.03)	-3.96 (-6.79,-1.12)	-3.66 (-6.45,-0.88)	-4.03 (-6.78,-1.29)
		M2 ^b	-3.04 (-5.46,-0.63)	-3.14 (-5.57,-0.71)	-3.03 (-5.45,-0.61)	-3.32 (-5.66,-0.98)
500m buffer	0.14	M1 ^a	-5.11 (-8.04,-2.18)	-5.24 (-8.18,-2.29)	-4.79 (-7.70,-1.89)	-5.23 (-8.07,-2.39)
		M2 ^b	-3.89 (-6.40,-1.37)	-4.00 (-6.53,-1.47)	-3.87 (-6.39,-1.35)	-4.13 (-6.56,-1.70)

961 Note: statistically significant beta coefficients are indicated in bold text (p-value < 0.05). Number of participants = 114 and number of repeated
 962 observations = 303.

963 ^aModel 1 (M1) adjusted for individual sociodemographic covariates (age, sex, BMI (kg/m²), nationality, education level, employment status),
 964 and area-level covariates (low-educated and foreign origin, temperature, relative humidity), with participant ID as random effect and city as
 965 fixed effect.

966 ^bModel 2 (M2) M1 additionally adjusted for fellow vessel diameter.

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Table S9. Descriptive characteristics of the study participants by sex.

Variable	Full sample	Men	Women	p-value	
<i>n participants</i>	114	53	61		
<i>n repeated observations</i>	303	143	160		
Individual level covariates					
Age	33 (12.8)	34 (13.0)	30 (13.0)	0.04	
Nationality country of study	98 (86.0%)	46 (86.8%)	52 (85.3%)	0.99	
Full-time employed	85 (74.6%)	43 (81.1%)	42 (68.9%)	0.20	
Higher education	102 (89.5%)	45 (84.9%)	57 (93.4%)	0.24	
Body mass index (BMI) ^a , kg/m ²	22.70 (4.5)	24.30 (4.4%)	22.16 (3.5%)	0.01	
Systolic blood pressure (SBP), mmHg	103 (16.5)	109.33 (11.2)	97.67 (11.8)	0.01	
Diastolic blood pressure (DBP), mmHg	68.67 (10.7)	71.33 (10.7)	66.33 (10.0)	0.01	
Mean arterial pressure (MAP) ^b , mmHg	79.89 (11.9)	83.67 (9.4)	76.83 (9.6)	0.01	
Area level covariates^c					
Percentage of population with low education	4.66 (8.0)	4.17 (8.5)	5.41 (7.1)	0.27	
Percentage of population with foreign origin	12.53 (27.1)	11.30 (27.2)	13.55 (26.8)	0.57	
Retinal vessel metric (µm)					
Central retinal arteriolar equivalent (CRAE)	160.79 (19.28)	159.71 (21.90)	162.84 (17.32)	0.05	
Central retinal venular equivalent (CRVE)	235.56 (25.82)	232.94 (21.67)	238.29 (25.80)	0.04	
Exposure measures					
<i>Surrounding greenness (seasonal NDVI)</i>					
home	100m buffer	0.34 (0.23)	0.39 (0.26)	0.30 (0.19)	0.01
	300m buffer	0.35 (0.22)	0.39 (0.25)	0.33 (0.17)	0.01
	500m buffer	0.36 (0.21)	0.41 (0.26)	0.33 (0.19)	0.01
work/school	100m buffer	0.24 (0.16)	0.26 (0.16)	0.22 (0.14)	0.01
	300m buffer	0.27 (0.14)	0.29 (0.18)	0.26 (0.13)	0.01
	500m buffer	0.29 (0.14)	0.31 (0.16)	0.26 (0.14)	0.01
<i>Ambient air pollution (µg/m³)</i>					

Black carbon (BC) ^d	1.34 (0.73)	1.25 (0.71)	1.38 (0.64)	0.21
<i>Other</i>				
Temperature, °C	14 (8.61)	13.79 (9.66)	14.08 (8.08)	0.64
Relative humidity	74 (17.00)	74.0 (16.50)	73.5 (15.00)	0.61

970 Note: descriptive statistics are presented as count (%) for categorical variables and as median (interquartile range) for continuous variables. P-
971 value of between-sex comparison is obtained using the chi-square test for categorical variables and the Wilcoxon rank-sum test for continuous
972 variables.

973 ^aBMI objective body weight not available for 3 participants, hence self-reported weight at time of baseline survey was used to calculate BMI.

974 ^bMAP = (2/3 * DBP) + (1/3 * SBP)

975 ^c Indicators of socioeconomic position at neighbourhood level based on census-derived indicators.

976 ^dBC: personal exposure obtained by microAeth wearable sensors

977 **Table S10.** Adjusted beta coefficients (β) and 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) of the association between retinal vessel diameter (CRAE and
 978 CRVE) and one interquartile increase (IQR) in 100m, 300m and 500m buffers for surrounding greenness (seasonal NDVI) by location (home
 979 and work/school) and by sex.
 980

		CRAE				
		full sample	sex		LRT p-value ^c	
seasonal NDVI	IQR		Men	Women		
		β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)		
<i>home</i>						
100m buffer	0.23	M1 ^a	-2.57 (-5.68,0.53)	-0.77 (-5.14,3.59)	-5.54 (-9.96,-1.11)	0.22
		M2 ^b	-1.19 (-3.88,1.49)	-0.14 (-3.85,3.58)	-3.20 (-7.20,0.79)	0.44
300m buffer	0.22	M1 ^a	-2.99 (-6.33,0.36)	-0.55 (-5.00,3.91)	-6.95 (-11.88,-2.01)	0.13
		M2 ^b	-1.14 (-4.02,1.73)	-0.35 (-4.12,3.42)	-3.19 (-7.70,1.30)	0.58
500m buffer	0.21	M1 ^a	-2.36 (-5.56,0.83)	0.15 (-3.99,4.29)	-7.02 (-11.87,-2.17)	0.10
		M2 ^b	-0.95 (-3.69,1.79)	0.07 (-3.45,3.59)	-3.56 (-7.98,0.86)	0.48
<i>work/school</i>						
100m buffer	0.16	M1 ^a	-0.19 (-2.53,2.15)	1.34 (-1.83,4.52)	-1.99 (-5.37,1.38)	0.37
		M2 ^b	0.54 (-1.43,2.51)	1.38 (-1.28,4.03)	-0.72 (-3.65,2.21)	0.53
300m buffer	0.14	M1 ^a	-1.74 (-3.83,0.35)	-0.31 (-3.04,2.42)	-3.25 (-6.35,-0.14)	0.30
		M2 ^b	-0.18 (-1.97,1.60)	0.88 (-1.42,3.19)	-1.53 (-4.25,1.20)	0.39
500m buffer	0.14	M1 ^a	-2.38 (-4.56,-0.21)	-0.56 (-3.48,2.36)	-4.09 (-7.26,-0.93)	0.18
		M2 ^b	-0.34 (-2.21,1.54)	1.08 (-1.39,3.55)	-1.92 (-4.74,0.92)	0.24

981 Note: statistically significant beta coefficients are indicated in bold text (p-value < 0.05). Number of participants = 114 and number of repeated
 982 observations = 303 of which 46% men and 54% women.

983 ^aModel 1 (M1) adjusted for individual sociodemographic covariates (age, sex, BMI (kg/m²), nationality, education level, employment status),
 984 and area-level covariates (low-educated and foreign origin, temperature, relative humidity), with participant ID as random effect and city as
 985 fixed effect.

986 ^bModel 2 (M2) M1 additionally adjusted for fellow vessel diameter.

987 ^cLRT p-values derived from the model fit comparing the main model with and without interaction term.

988 **Table S10.** (Continued). Adjusted beta coefficients (β) and 95% confidence intervals (95% CI) of the association between retinal vessel diameter
 989 (CRAE and CRVE) and one interquartile increase (IQR) in 100m, 300m and 500m buffers for surrounding greenness (seasonal NDVI) by
 990 location (home and work/school) and by sex.
 991

		CRVE				
		full sample	sex		LRT p-value ^c	
			Men	Women		
seasonal NDVI	IQR	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)	β (95% CI)		
<i>home</i>						
100m buffer	0.23	M1 ^a	-3.57 (-7.69,0.54)	-1.27 (-6.56,4.03)	-7.02 (-13.24,-0.80)	0.29
		M2 ^b	-1.83 (-5.47,1.81)	-0.97 (-5.51,3.57)	-3.66 (-9.39,2.07)	0.63
300m buffer	0.22	M1 ^a	-4.84 (-9.31,-0.37)	-0.46 (-5.89,4.97)	-11.40 (-18.36,-4.44)	0.05
		M2 ^b	-2.82 (-6.73,1.10)	-0.20 (-4.84,4.45)	-7.31 (-13.90,-0.92)	0.16
500m buffer	0.21	M1 ^a	-3.94 (-8.20,0.33)	0.03 (-5.02,5.07)	-10.69 (-17.56,-3.82)	0.04
		M2 ^b	-2.34 (-6.07,1.39)	-0.12 (-4.44,4.19)	-6.68 (-12.99,-0.36)	0.16
<i>work/school</i>						
100m buffer	0.16	M1 ^a	-1.63 (-4.79,1.53)	0.48 (-3.45,4.42)	-3.95 (-8.77,0.88)	0.41
		M2 ^b	-1.78 (-4.49,0.92)	-0.67 (-4.02,2.67)	-2.78 (-7.04,1.47)	0.71
300m buffer	0.14	M1 ^a	-3.85 (-6.67,-1.03)	-2.36 (-5.72,1.00)	-5.14 (-9.63,-0.64)	0.56
		M2 ^b	-3.04 (-5.46,-0.63)	-2.35 (-5.20,0.49)	-3.34 (-7.33,0.64)	0.87
500m buffer	0.14	M1 ^a	-5.12 (-8.04,-2.18)	-3.36 (-6.95,0.22)	-6.46 (-11.03,-1.89)	0.52
		M2 ^b	-3.89 (-6.40,-1.37)	-3.18 (-6.20,-0.15)	-4.19 (-8.29,-0.09)	0.90

992 Note: statistically significant beta coefficients are indicated in bold text (p-value < 0.05). Number of participants = 114 and number of repeated
 993 observations = 303 of which 46% men and 54% women.

994 ^aModel 1 (M1) adjusted for individual sociodemographic covariates (age, sex, BMI (kg/m²), nationality, education level, employment status),
 995 and area-level covariates (low-educated and foreign origin, temperature, relative humidity), with participant ID as random effect and city as
 996 fixed effect.

997 ^bModel 2 (M2) M1 additionally adjusted for fellow vessel diameter.

998 ^cLRT p-values derived from the model fit comparing the main model with and without interaction term

